

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ALAAK****FIRST NAME: LUAL****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author uses Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 3%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the concept of academic writing in the Turabian booklet?

- The concept of academic writing includes a detailed research outline, questions, plans, preparations, readings, answers to hypothetical questions, and literature reviews. The various stages of drafting are crucial concepts in academic writing,
- Sound academic writing starts with an excellent introduction to the essay. It captures other things, such as the problems and thesis, and it is structured in such ways as to give answers to hypotheses. Ideas**

are required to flow and be supported by both sides of arguments logically.¹

- A nonfiction Academic writing comprises valid arguments, concepts and theories, a conclusion, and a list of Bibliographies.

2. What are the components of research proposals to students?

- Research is vital to all students regardless of areas of specialization and discipline. Literature review, methodology, top supervisory committee approval, information and facts finding and analysis.
- Research question, Literature review, methodology, problem statement, theories, and concepts incorporation into a research paper.²**
- Gathering of credible sources, data collection, and facts integration into a dissertation for academic requirements
- Helps in filtering source citations while acknowledging the work of others and helping readers judge the reliability and check the accuracy of the arguments.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 17.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 220.

3. **How do Bibliography and citations become a source of disappointment to many students?**

- Source citation and compilation of correct bibliography are essential, and non-compliance leads to poor grades. Lack of knowledge on the proper form of bibliography and incorrect referencing causes undesired outcomes.
- Academic paper must be supported with references and bibliographies using formats provided by instructions, basic patterns, order of elements, arrangement of entries, and referencing notes in text.³**
- Its other functions include finding relevant data in the form of Endnote and Note-Bibliography.
- Notes-bibliography is widely used in humanities and some social sciences, while the author-date style is applicable in natural and physical sciences. It has been noted that Euclid University prefers the use of the Turabian style guide, while other universities use APA and Oxford referencing styles.

³ Turabian, 139-140.

4. **How does the proper use of writing style play an important role in school success?**

- The writing style includes a clear layout in the form of headings and subheadings. This enhances readability and assists in coherent flow,
- It can guarantee success when supported by literature review and conforms that are preferred and considered acceptable in academic writing.⁴**
- It commences with an introduction of the topic, followed by evidence-based arguments. The thesis or dissertation should be in the introduction, while arguments are incorporated in the body, summarizing all the points.

5. **What are the roles of punctuation and other marks in an essay?**

- The punctuation and quotation marks break the lines and assist and give respect to fundamental English rules,
- Each includes full stop, quotation marks, quotes, exclamation marks, and apostrophes.⁵**

⁴ Turabian, 373.

⁵ Turabian, 371.

- These are essential in separating exact words quoted in double quotation marks when quoting a passage of less than five lines.

6. **What makes the European Union’s writing style different from other writing styles?**

- The style guide and references of the European Union style were adopted for use in the European Union. It has its unique style of writing and formats for the benefit of EU Member States and authorizes only the use of British English,
- It respects language usage such as American and British English, for example, consistency rather than using the two interchangeably.⁶**
- It recognizes full stops, Commas, dashes, brackets, question marks, forward slashes, apostrophes, ellipses, punctuation, names of people, and natural phenomena in EU guide style with Turabian. Use a semicolon rather than a comma to combine two sentences into one without linking conjunction.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 4th ed.* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 24.

7. Is the Turabian style guide more important than Oxford or APA, and does it play a similar function in an academic fraternity?

- The Turabian referencing style is the only acceptable guide at Euclid University. This does not mean that other referencing styles provided in Oxford and APA are not necessary,
- Euclid expects students to use the Turabian rule of style, though health students use the Turabian or WHO rules of style or both.⁷**
- Referencing style is typical in most essays because it is used to acknowledge words or statements of authors.

8. What are the crucial concepts in the dissertation?

- The dissertation, author name, department, title, abstracts or introduction, university and place, table of contents, acknowledgments, body, and conclusion/recommendations. Other such as structures, chapters, subtitles, and more development of detailed and systematic methods of investigation on a research topic are crucial,

⁷ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2.

Organization of dissertation documents, abstract, introduction, heading and subheadings, theories and concepts integration, and conclusions.⁸

author name, academic institution, dissertation title, supervisory committee, and principal supervisor, list of references, and literature review

9. **What are the components of a dissertation that meet academic standards?**

It should have a precise title to act as a guide. It should contain a table of contents, outline, chapters, research variables, participants, and setting or the research's treatment, variables, participants, and setting,

Title is followed by chapter one with research questions and answers; other chapters may introduce discoveries and analysis of bibliographic databases. Theses and dissertations are cited much like books except for the title, which is in Roman type and enclosed in quotation marks. After the author, date, and title, list the kind of paper and the academic institution.⁹

⁸ Turabian, 202-204.

⁹ Turabian, 275-280.

- Consistency and coherence of the dissertation guide the researcher from losing track of the research topic.

10. **What are the crucial components of quantitative and qualitative dissertation research?**

- Quantitative studies rely on numerical or measurable data. In contrast, qualitative studies rely on personal accounts or documents that illustrate in detail.
- Ethics, planning, and development of questionnaires are crucial elements of quantitative and qualitative methodologies; this is a brief research proposal that describes what might be studied in the proposed dissertation.**¹⁰
- Both quantitative and qualitative are the cornerstones of research methodology used interchangeably during research, data collection, and data analysis. It uses sample collections, analysis and tabulation, confidentiality, and honest interpretation of results. Guidance on the concept paper, pre-prospectus, and introduction to the chapter plan.

¹⁰ Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Tallahassee: (Florida State University, 2017), 7.

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